

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

An invariant based transversely isotropic constitutive model for unidirectional polymer composites considering the matrix viscous effects

P.-W. Gerbaud, F. Otero, P. Bussetta and P. P. Camanho

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Introduction - Motivation

- The diversity and number of applications in which Fibres Reinforced Polymers (FRPs) are used are increasing
- Composite structures may be subjected to high-speed loading events (e.g. bird or hail impact, tire explosion or crash events)

Constitutive model description - background

- Initially, Vogler et al. (2013) developed an elastic-plastic model capable of well predicting the behavior of UniDirectional (UD) plies of FRPs, but not considering the viscous effects
- The model has been first upgraded to take into account the observed viscous behavior for high strain-rates in the plastic response (Vogler et al. (2015))
- In order to calibrate that model, scaling functions were used to model the experimentally observed viscoelastic behavior (Koerber et al. (2018))
- A new extension to consider viscoelastic effect for the fully three-dimensional transversely isotropic viscoplastic model for UD laminates is presented

Constitutive model description - formulation

- The viscoelastic extension implemented is based on a generalized Maxwell model

- C_0 is the original elastic modulus of the material (quasi-static property).
- There is another branch in parallel characterized by its elastic modulus C_1 and its relaxation time τ_1

Constitutive model description - formulation

- For the 3D formulation, the viscoelastic prediction is

$$\begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{n+1} &= \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{ve}^{n+1}, \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{\text{pred},n+1} &= \boldsymbol{\sigma}_0^n + f_1^{n+1} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_1^n + \mathbb{C}_{ve}^{n+1} : \Delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{n+1}, \end{cases}$$

with $f_1^{n+1} = e^{(-\Delta t^{n+1}/\tau_1)}$, and $f_2^{n+1} = \frac{1 - e^{(-\Delta t^{n+1}/\tau_1)}}{\Delta t^{n+1}/\tau_1}$ $\mathbb{C}_{ve}^{n+1} = [\mathbb{0} + f_2^{n+1} \mathbb{T}_1] : \mathbb{C}_0$.

- The relaxation tensor (using the Voigt notation) for a transverse isotropic material in the material coordinate system (1 is the direction of the fibre) is

$$\hat{\Gamma} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_{11} & \gamma_{12} & \gamma_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \gamma_{21} & \gamma_{22} & \gamma_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \gamma_{21} & \gamma_{23} & \gamma_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \gamma_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \gamma_{44} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \gamma_{66} \end{bmatrix}$$

Constitutive model description - formulation

- The stress tensor is decomposed in “viscous inducing” stresses and assumed “elastic reaction” stresses

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{e, \text{reac}} + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{vp, \text{ind}},$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{e, \text{reac}} = p\mathbf{I} + \sigma_f \mathbf{A},$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{vp, \text{ind}} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} - \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{e, \text{reac}} = \mathbf{s}.$$

- For elastic part, the “viscoelasticity inducing” stresses are

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{ve, \text{ind}} = \mathbb{P}_{ve, \text{ind}} : \boldsymbol{\sigma}. \quad \mathbb{P}_{ve, \text{ind}} = \mathbb{I} - \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{I} - \frac{3}{2} \mathbf{A} \otimes \mathbf{A} + \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{A} \otimes \mathbf{I} + \mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{A}).$$

- Then, the relaxation tensor can be expressed as

$$\Gamma_1 = \gamma_{ve, 1} \mathbb{P}_{ve, \text{ind}}.$$

Constitutive model description - formulation

- The viscoplastic formulation, proposed by Vogler et al. (2015)

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{vp,ind} = \mathbb{P}_{vp,ind} : \boldsymbol{\sigma}, \quad \mathbb{P}_{vp,ind} = \mathbb{P}_{ve,ind}.$$

- The viscoplastic creep function and potential are defined as

$$f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \bar{\varepsilon}_{vp}, \mathbf{A}) = \alpha_1 I_1 + \alpha_2 I_2 + \alpha_3 I_3 + \alpha_{32} I_3^2 - 1 \leq 0,$$

$$g(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \mathbf{A}) = \beta_1 I_1 + \beta_2 I_2 + \beta_3 I_3^2 - 1.$$

$$I_1 = \frac{1}{2} \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{vp,ind}^2) - \underline{a} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{vp,ind}^2) \underline{a},$$

$$I_2 = \underline{a} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{vp,ind}^2) \underline{a},$$

$$I_3 = \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}) - \underline{a} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{vp,ind} \underline{a},$$

Calibration of the viscous parameters

- The IM7-8552 UD Carbon/Epoxy material system was used.
- The calibration of the two viscoelastic parameters is done performing the 90° compression tests.
- For the material study, just two strain rate regimes were tested. Consequently, the parameter m is set to $m = 1$.
- To calibrate the viscoplastic parameter η , the axial stress-strain curves of the 45° off-axis compression tests are used.

Parameter name	Value	Unit
m	1	—
η	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$	Ns/mm ²
τ_1	$1 \cdot 10^{-2}$	s
$\gamma_{ve,1}$	0.35	—

Comparison with experimental data

- The model is implemented in the commercial software Abaqus/Explicit through a VUMAT user material
- The simulated cases are off-axis 15° , 30° , 45° and 90° transverse tension and off-axis 15° , 30° , 45° , 60° , 75° and 90° transverse compression.
- The meshes used and applied boundary conditions are

Comparison with experimental data - tension

Comparison with experimental data - compression

Conclusions

- A fully 3D viscoelastic-viscoplastic model was presented.
- The viscoelastic formulation was expressed within the framework of the invariant theory.
- The model was calibrated for the material system Hexcel IM7-8552.
- The simulated results for the off-axis and transverse tension and compression cases present a very good correlation with the available experimental data.

Thank you!

It gratefully acknowledge the funding of Project NORTE-01-0145-FEDER-000022 SciTech Science and Technology for Competitive and Sustainable Industries, co-financed by Programa Operacional Regional do Norte (NORTE2020), through Fundo Europeu de Desenvolvimento Regional (FEDER).

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